

Scotland: A Tale of Internal Strife and Nation-Building

Matthew Vincent Braccia

Chaminade High School

AP World History: Modern

June 3, 2024

Scotland's history from the 13th to the 20th century was defined by internal conflicts and attempts at nation-building among its diverse population. The region wasn't colonized externally but faced divisions among the Lowlanders and Highlanders known collectively as Scots and settlers from the rest of The British Isles. Lowlanders, mostly in the south, had ties to England and overall were more friendly to them due to the common religion of Protestantism and the mutual integrability of their languages of Scots and English, while Highlanders maintained clan-based societies and a unique religion and language until much later which often came into conflict with the English and Lowlanders. The English influenced politics and economics. Socio-economic changes, like the Highland Clearances which for the most part many Lowlanders and Scots Nobel men were complicit in and unproportionally, affected the Highlanders. Despite these challenges, Scots aimed to assert autonomy and were able to forge a unified identity and nation-state within Scotland and the British Isle as a whole. Understanding these internal struggles is key to understanding Scotland's history and its impact today. From the 13th to the 19th century, Scotland's history was characterized by internal strife between Lowlanders and Highlanders and efforts to unify these groups into a cohesive nation-state. This was a centuries-old problem rooted in competing power claims, An attempt for everyone to preserve their own culture and at the same time the attempt to create a nation-state and nation-building processes within the region but was not the colonization of a nation.

The internal conflicts between Lowlanders, British, and Highlanders was a century-old problem rooted in competing claims to power and the attempt to preserve distinct regional identities from each other while at the same time from a unified nation-state from 1200 to 1800. The internal power struggles highlight the nation's efforts to centralize authority and build a unified state. As seen in the quote, “At the death of James V. it might seem that Scotland was less

a united nation than it had been at the death of his father.” (Brown 257). This extract underscores the internal power struggles within Scotland during the reign of James IV and the transition from noble dominance to centralized royal authority as a crucial step in the nation-building process. This emphasizes the internal conflicts and struggle of power predating any predominant English involvement in Scotland and shows efforts to establish a unified nation-state for the many people of Scotland since a very early time.

Another source that supports this idea is some of the historical maps of Scotland found in the Scottish National Library. These two maps show the division of Scotland between lowland and highlanders politically in 1697 and 1822 respectively (Lizars 1822)(Allard 1697). These maps help to highlight the division between Highland and Lowland regions highlighting the governance and cultural disparities within Scotland from within the Scots themselves and the decrease in the highlanders' governance and way of life over time as the area where traditional Highlander chiefdom have decreased over this circa 150 years period.

The final piece of deviance that supports this idea is found in *The Politics of Highland Land Reform* which depicts the politics of Highland land reform in the late 19th century, demonstrating how economic transformations fueled internal conflicts and resistance to centralized control (Hunter 6). This reveals how socioeconomic changes, such as the Highland Clearances, contributed to the fragmentation and destruction of certain parts of Scottish society, mostly the highlanders' way of life as the attempts at centralization and nation-building by trying to kickstart the economy with the expansion of sheep farms which were highly profitable but at the expense of the highlanders which were kicked off their land and Ethier force to go work in the lowlands cities or migrant to place like the United States or Canada.

Overall these sources of *The Molding of the Scottish Nation*, Scottish maps, and *The Politics of the Highland Reform*, help make clear and promote that the conflicts between Lowlanders, British, and Highlanders were century-old problems rooted in competing claims to power, and many sacrifices and injustice were made in the name of nation-building and centralization. These processes were necessary to create a unified Scottish state and culture that previously did not exist and without them, Scotland would be an extremely less United place and the idea of a shared Scottish identity would not exist.

The internal conflicts between Lowlanders, British, and Highlanders also stemmed from the attempt to create a nation-state and nation-building processes in Great Britain as a whole from 1700 to 1900. This idea is the main basis of the United Kingdom's founding document The Act of Union 1707 which states “That all the Subjects of the United Kingdom of Great-Britain shall, from and after the Union, have full Freedom and Intercourse of Trade and Navigation, to and from any Port or Place within the said united Kingdom, and the Dominions and Plantations thereunto belonging; and that there be a Communication of all other Rights, Privileges, and Advantages, which do or may belong to the Subjects of either Kingdom, except where it is otherwise expressly agreed in these Articles.”(British Parliament article 4). The Act of Union 1707 was a pivotal moment in Scottish history, facilitating economic stability and centralization. While it led to some loss of autonomy, it also integrated Scottish and English economies, benefiting many Lowlanders. However, Highlanders, focused on preserving their unique culture and government, viewed this union with skepticism.

Another piece of evidence that supports this idea of creating a unified Scottish/British identity and state is seen in the quote “For years, reading lists of the great universities of

Edinburgh and Glasgow were compiled without any of her contributions to the Scottish cannon. Was she even Scottish? readers might wonder” (Interdisciplinary Reader 12) This shows that many in Scotland think that Scottish is not just a racial identity but also a cultural identity and people can “become Scottish” which is an important idea of a nation-state to unify all people in Scotland and united kingdom under this idea of being all Scottish/British no matter if your a highlander, lowlander or in this case someone born to non-British immigrant parents in Scotland. In essence, a key conflict at this time was to build a united Scottish/British identity and nation at this time that previously was not widespread and faced much resistance by people who wanted to preserve their more local identity and not be associated with this larger group.

This internal conflict between the Lowlanders, British, and Highlanders however was not the domination and colonization of the Scots by an outside power. As seen in the capstone the events that occurred in Scotland are not how the English colonization As seen in the capstone reader British colonies at this time were settlers colonies where the British sent settlers over to a place to create a colony that for the sole economic benefit of the British were natives had no little rights (Capstone Reader 26-30). Even at their height of centralized power around Westminster English only made up a small percentage of the actual ruling and upper class in Scotland which was throughout most of history dominated by the lowlanders much to the dismay of the highlanders and all Scots legally were always equal with the English unlike the native people of their colonies which were legally lesser in many cases in their colonies.

This same idea is also shared by the shared studies in which our Nigerian counterpart explained the colonization of their people and how they were deprived of basically all human rights and where many people and cultures were put into one British-made country with the only

thing they have in common is being oppressed by the British. (Shared Studios) In Scotland this was not the case remotely; it was a unified kingdom for centuries before the English came and under the law lowlanders and highlanders were given the same full legal rights as any other citizen in the United Kingdom. These both help to illustrate that the internal conflict in Scotland was not colonization by the English of the Scots but an attempt to create a unified nation-state by the Scots from 1300 to 1700 and then by the British from 1700 to 1900. Both of these sources help to show that the events that took place in Scotland were not colonization because the events that took place in settler colonies didn't take place and the events that took place in resource colonies like Nigeria didn't occur.

In conclusion, these internal conflicts between Lowlanders, Highlanders, and British settlers played a crucial role in shaping Scotland's history, culture, and nation-state from the 13th to the 20th century. These conflicts were not a result of external colonization but were driven by regional power struggles and efforts to build originally a unified Scottish nation-state and later a unified British nation-state. Understanding these dynamics provides valuable insights into Scotland's historical identity and its lasting impact explains the current state of Scotland as a county of the United Kingdom and balances being part of this as well as keeping its own cultural identity at the same time.

Works Cited

Allard, Carel. "Novissima Regni Scotiae septentrionalis et meridionalis tabula, divisae in ducatus, comitatus, vice-comitatus, provincias, praefecturas, dominia et insulas." [Map] Amsterdam : Allard, [1697]. [Online] Available at: <https://maps.nls.uk/countries/scotland/rec/154>

Brown, P. Hume. "The Moulding of the Scottish Nation." *The Scottish Historical Review*, vol. 1, no. 3, 1904, pp. 245–59. JSTOR, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25517486>. Accessed 22 May 2024.

Chaminade High School Capstone Reader

Chaminade High School Interdisciplinary Reader

Great Britain. Parliament. "Act of Union 1706." 1706. Parliament.uk, www.parliament.uk/globalassets/documents/heritage/articlesofunion.pdf.

Hunter, James. "The Politics of Highland Land Reform, 1873-1895." *The Scottish Historical Review*, vol. 53, no. 155, 1974, pp. 45–68. JSTOR, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25529057>. Accessed 22 May 2024.

Lizars, W. H. (William Home), 1788-1859. *Map of the Highlands of Scotland denoting the districts or counties inhabited by the Highland Clans*. Edinburgh: A. Constable & Co., 1822. [Online] Available at: <https://maps.nls.uk/countries/scotland/rec/864>

